

CYCLIC BUCKLING UNDER COMBINED LOADS OF COMPOSITE PANELS

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SUMMARY

Experimental results obtained on CFRP panels subjected to static and cyclic combined loadings in compression and shear are presented. Some of the panels present pre-damaged areas in correspondence of the stringers. Results show that this kind of structures, even with pre-damages, can well work under cyclic post-buckling loads.

Keywords: Cyclic buckling, post-buckling field, CFRP panels

INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced composites are an important class of engineering materials due to their high specific mechanical properties. Unlike isotropic materials, they offer a not well-known behaviour in the post-buckling field,^{1,2} especially when the buckling load is reached thousands of times during the operative life. Indeed, in literature, very few results³ are available on how cyclic buckling under combined loading influences the non-linear behaviour of CFRP aeronautical panels and their collapse. This leads to the necessity to conduct an intensive investigation of the damage onset in composite structures subjected to different load conditions.

Some results obtained during the COCOMAT European project⁴ on stringer stiffened composite panels subjected to static and cyclic buckling under combined compression and shear loading are here presented. In particular, the first part of present paper summarizes the results obtained on two undamaged panels, assembled in close box configuration and loaded under several combination of axial compression and shear. The second part of the paper resumes the results obtained on two pre-damaged panels individually loaded under axial compression.

The idea behind the closed box configuration is that in this way it is possible to load each panel under shear by applying a torque on the whole box⁵. Besides, both static and cyclic loads are investigated.

PANELS

Four CFRP panels are manufactured by Israel Aeronautical Industries (IAI) and tested at Technion, Haifa, Israel and at Politecnico di Milano, Milan, Italy. They are 720 *mm* high, with a radius of curvature of 938 *mm*, and are made with unidirectional carbon composite material. Panels present five blade stringer stiffeners, which are directly co-cured to the skin during the manufacturing process. The length of the blades is 20 *mm*, while the part in contact with the skin is 60 *mm* width. Panels are provided with two ending tabs, allowing the clamping into the loading machines. Table 1 summarizes the geometrical properties and the lay-up of the panels.

Table 1 Geometrical properties and lay-up of the panels.

Radius of curvature	938 <i>mm</i>
Total height	720 <i>mm</i>
Arc-length	660 <i>mm</i>
Stringer blade length	20 <i>mm</i>
Stringer thickness	3 <i>mm</i>
Skin thickness	1 <i>mm</i>
Skin lay-up	$[0^\circ/+45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ]_S$
Stringer lay-up	$[+45^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ_2]_{3S}$

The first two panels, named COCOMAT 5 and COCOMAT 6, are assembled in a closed box, named Box A, which was tested at Politecnico di Milano under several combinations of axial compression and torque. The box is built connecting two CFRP stiffened curved panels with two flat lateral aluminium plates, as shown in Figure 1, where only half structure is reported. The box is obtained assembling two undamaged panels.

Figure 1 shows also the strain gauge position. In particular, on the back panel, strain gauges are placed in a back-to-back configuration, both on the skin and on the stringers; while on the front panel they are bonded only on the stiffeners, in order to leave the skin free for the out-of-plane deformation measurements by a laser sensor equipment of Politecnico di Milano.

Fig. 1 CFRP curved panel and lateral aluminium plate (half closed box structure).

The other two panels, named COCOMAT 7 and COCOMAT 8, were tested under pure axial compression at Technion. These panels presented a Teflon insert between stringers and skin in three areas. The location of the pre-damaged areas is reported in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 Map and types of the artificial damages.

Moreover, on panel COCOMAT 8, some impacts are performed using air gun, in addition to the pre-damages realized with Teflon inserts, in the vicinity of the artificial delaminations. The sizes and the locations of the impact areas are given in Figure 3 and in Figure 4. Close ups of the shapes of the impact damage, that are introduced into the panel, are also depicted in Figure 4.

Fig. 3 Locations of the strain gages, of the axial and lateral LVDT's and of the damage induced by the air gun (in orange) on panel COCOMAT8.

Fig. 4 Panel COCOMAT8 - Damage induced by the air gun:
 (a) front of the panel; (b), (c), (d) close ups; (e) back of the middle stringer.

RESULTS ON CLOSED BOX UNDER COMBINED LOADING

The testing procedure was decided together with IAI, in order to apply loading conditions as close as possible to those really experienced by these structures during their operative life.

At first, nine static tests were performed on the box, in order to record the interaction curve:

- One pure axial compression test;
- Two pure torsion tests (one in the clockwise and one in the counter-clockwise direction). To prevent tension stresses in the panel, a small axial compression load (30 *kN*) was applied and kept constant in these two tests.
- Three combined tests keeping a constant axial compression and reaching the buckling load by increasing the torque in the clockwise direction and three combined tests keeping a constant axial compression and reaching the buckling load by increasing the torque in the counter-clockwise direction. In the combined tests, the axial load was equal to 41 *kN*, 82 *kN* and 123 *kN*, respectively.

The results obtained in the static tests performed on the box are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2 Results of static buckling tests on box A.

Test	Buckling compression [<i>kN</i>]	Buckling torque [<i>kNm</i>]
Axial compression	164	0
CW torque	30	9.8
CCW torque	30	-10.0
Combined 1	41	-9.2
Combined 2	82	-6.3
Combined 3	123	-3.6
Combined 4	41	8.7
Combined 5	82	5.8
Combined 6	123	3.2

Figure 5 presents the axial compression vs. shortening curve and the two torque vs. rotation curves obtained, respectively, during the pure compression, the pure clockwise and the pure counter-clockwise torque tests. Figure 6 reports the buckling interaction curve recorded during the static tests.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 5 Box A: (a) axial compression test; (b) clockwise torque test; (c) counter-clockwise torque test.

Fig. 6 Box A: interaction curve.

The box was then tested at 0.2 *Hz*, with a fixed axial compression equal to 30 *kN*, under cyclic torsion, in the counter-clockwise direction, as follows:

- 2000 cycles cycling the torque from 0 *kNm* to 15 *kNm*;
- 2000 cycles cycling the torque from 0 *kNm* to 20 *kNm*;
- 12000 cycles cycling the torque from 0 *kNm* to 25 *kNm*.

For the first two sequences the behaviour of the box was investigated every 500 cycles measuring the torque vs. rotation curve, the strain distribution and the deformed shape, while for the third sequence the behaviour of the box was investigated, after 1000, 2000, 7000 and 12000 cycles.

Figure 7 presents the comparison of four torque vs. rotation curves recorded during the third sequence. It is possible to note that the effect of applied cyclic post-buckling torque is negligible: no changes were observed in the initial linear field, and in the post-buckling range. The same observation can be done by comparing the strain distribution and the deformed shape of the box. As an example, Figure 8 presents the deformed shapes acquired by the laser equipment at maximum reached loads during the third sequence of cyclic loading.

Fig. 7 Box A: torque vs. rotation curves measured during the third sequence of cyclic loading (maximum torque = 25 kNm).

Fig. 8 Box A: laser scan of front panel during the third cyclic sequence (axial load fixed to 30 kN, maximum torque = 25 kNm) after (a) 1000, (b) 2000, (c) 7000 and (d) 12000 cycles.

Finally, the box was statically collapsed keeping a constant axial compression of 30 *kN* and reaching the collapse by increasing the torque.

Figure 9 and Figure 10 report, respectively, the torque vs. rotation curve and a comparison between a photo with moiré fringes and a laser scan of the front panel obtained during the collapse test.

Fig. 9 Box A: torque vs. rotation curve obtained in collapse test.

Fig. 10 Box A: photo with moiré fringes and laser scan during the collapse test (compression = 30 *kN*; torque = 50 *kNm*).

RESULTS ON PRE-DAMAGED PANELS UNDER COMPRESSION

Damage is a major factor that has to be considered during the study of repeated loading of a structure, particularly in the case of repeated buckling in post-buckling range, where deformations are significantly large. To investigate the influence of damage on repeated buckling, two panels were tested under axial compression, COCOMAT 7 and COCOMAT 8. Both panels contained local initial disbonding in their three central stringers. The disbonding was obtained by inserting pieces of Teflon layers in the designated damage locations to represent the required local flaws.

The first panel, COCOMAT 7, was at first statically tested. It buckled at 63.8 *kN* with a single wave, while a fully developed waves pattern appeared at 102 *kN*. Then the panel was cycled in the range of 0-150 *kN* for 2000 cycles, without any visible reduction in the axial stiffness. The panel completed 52000 cycles in that load range, complemented by another 10000 cycles in the range of 0-180 *kN* and another 1820 cycles in the range of 0-200 *kN*. The load vs. shortening curves recorded during the cyclic tests are reported in Figure 11, while the readings of the strain gages after 61500 cycles are shown in Figure 12.

Fig. 11 Panel COCOMAT 7: load vs. shortening curves measured during the cyclic loading.

Fig. 12 Panel COCOMAT 7: strain gages readings vs. axial compression load after 61500 cycles.

During the cycle 63821 the panel collapsed under 158.7 kN, due to the local failure of one of the stringers (Figure 13).

Fig. 13 Panel COCOMAT 7: damage after collapse.

Although the panel collapsed at 158.7 kN, it sustained a load equal to 200 kN during the repeated loading. Figure 14 presents the development of the post-buckling wave pattern.

Fig. 14 Panel COCOMAT 7: development of the buckling pattern
(a) at 63.8 kN ; (b) at 170.0 kN .

Test results of panel COCOMAT 7 did not reveal any degradation due to the artificial damage that was introduced during the manufacturing process. Consequently, it was decided to introduce impacts in three areas to amplify the influence of damage presence on the integrity of a panel and consequently its behaviour.

Like the previous panel, panel COCOMAT 8 was first statically tested and buckled under 90 kN with a fully developed waves pattern. It was found that this buckling capacity agrees well with the test results corresponding to COCOMAT 7. Then it was repeatedly cycled in the range of 0-150 kN for 2000 cycles, without any visible reduction in the axial stiffness.

The panel completed 50000 cycles in that loading range without experiencing any reduction in its stiffness or growth in damage, as it is shown in Figure 15, where the axial compression vs. shortening curves recorded during the cyclic tests are reported. Hence, the presence of the preliminary extended damage had no influence on the response of the panel, even under repeated buckling. The readings of the strain gages after 50000 cycles are shown in Figure 16.

Fig. 15 Panel COCOMAT 8: load vs. shortening curves measured during the cyclic loading.

Fig. 16 Panel COCOMAT8: strain gages readings vs. axial compression load after 50000 cycles.

The panel collapsed under a load of 201.1 kN in very good agreement with the test results of COCOMAT 7. Figure 17 presents the development of the post-buckling wave pattern, while Figure 18 shows the damage after collapse due to breakage of fibres and tearing of the skin. COCOMAT 8 also exhibits a high margin between buckling and collapse.

Fig. 17 Panel COCOMAT 8: development of the buckling pattern
(a) at 61.5 kN; (b) at 103 kN.

Fig. 18 Panel COCOMAT 8: damage after collapse.

CONCLUSIONS

Four curved stringer-stiffened composite panels, manufactured by IAI (Israel Aeronautical Industries), were tested at Politecnico di Milano and at Technion to yield the first buckling and the post-buckling behaviour till collapse. All the panels underwent repeated cyclic post-buckling loading in relatively deep post-buckling region. The first two panels, initially undamaged, were assembled in a closed box configuration so to test each panel under combined axial compression and shear loading by applying an axial compression and a torque on the box. As far as the remaining two panels are concerned, the first one contains artificial type damage (Teflon inserts), while the second one contains both artificial and impact induced damage, were tested under pure axial compression.

The results demonstrated that neither repeated buckling under combined loading, within the number of cycles applied in the present program, nor the artificial damage and the induced impact damage, that were introduced into the panels, resulted in stiffness degradation of the panels.

No premature failure was observed in the tested panels within their expected life cycle, i.e. exposure to few hundred of cycles in the deep post-buckling region, even in presence of combination damage types.

Besides, no skin-stringer separation was encountered till collapse of the panels.

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